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FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH THE SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION OF
TELEHEALTH

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice project was to identify factors that support adoption of telehealth in a for-profit retail health clinic. A cross-sectional design was employed to address project aims. Nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses from four southern California counties completed an online survey in fall 2014, which included demographic items as well as a telehealth adoption tool adapted from the Instrument to Measure Perceptions of Adopting an Information Technology Innovation. This instrument measures five diffusion of innovations theory (DIT) constructs (relative advantage, compatibility, trialability, observability, complexity) as well as result demonstrability, voluntariness, and image. Three open-ended questions were also included. The DIT and Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services model (PARiSH) provided theoretical and conceptual foundations for this project. Sixty-three nurses from this retail health clinic completed the survey (response rate 68%). Of these, 43% worked in high-adoption counties (regions achieving 77% of all telehealth visits). High adopters and low adopters (those underutilizing the innovation of telehealth) did not differ in terms of years of experience, levels of education, and months on telehealth at baseline. Significantly different were nurse responses to the voluntariness construct: “My boss requires me to use telehealth” and “Although it might be helpful, using telehealth is compulsory in my job” with high adopters perceiving these more positively. Two items measuring compatibility were significantly associated with telehealth adoption: “I think that using telehealth fits well with the way I like to work”

and “Using telehealth fits into my work style” with low adopters perceiving both items more negatively. To improve adoption of telehealth, organizational leadership may want to consider strategies to improve perceived voluntariness and compatibility. For example, champions could be assigned to oversee the low-adopter clinics to offer expert support and provide encouragement to reduce the challenges associated with the stress of a new innovation.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vi
LIST OF FIGURES.....	viii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	ix
BACKGROUND.....	1
Problem Statement.....	1
Purpose Statement.....	4
Supporting Framework.....	5
PARIHS Conceptual Model.....	5
Diffusion of Innovations Theory.....	9
REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....	11
Overview.....	11
Perceptions of Innovation.....	12
Relative Advantage.....	12
Trialability.....	13
Complexity.....	15
Compatibility.....	16
Observability.....	19
METHODS.....	21
Independent Variables.....	22
Outcome Variables.....	22
Analysis.....	23
RESULTS.....	24
DISCUSSION.....	28

Additional Considerations with Telehealth Adoption	33
Limitations	33
CONCLUSION.....	35
REFERENCES	36
APPENDIX A: TABLES OF EVIDENCE	39
APPENDIX B: TABLE: UNIVARIATE ANALYSIS OF LIKERT SCALE QUESTIONS	46
APPENDIX C: CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH	48
APPENDIX D: SURVEY QUESTIONS.....	50

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Bivariate of Telehealth Questionnaire and Demographic Characteristic	26

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. PARiHS framework conceptualization.....	6
2. Rogers' conceptualization of Diffusion of Innovations.....	9
3. Respondent's Professional Role in the Organization	24
4. Respondent's Level of Education	25
5. Survey Quality Question 12.....	25

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BACKGROUND

Problem Statement

One of the most critical aspects of managing illness is the active and open communication between patients and their healthcare providers. Currently our healthcare system provides only episodic face-to-face care, little contact during the interval between interactions, and poor coordination of care over time (Estes et al., 2013). Subsequently, there is increased interest in exploring technological innovations to improve healthcare interactions and optimize patient outcomes.

The population of the United States continues to grow. In particular, the older American population is expected to increase from 35 million (in 2000) to 72 million, or 20 percent of the total U.S. population by 2030 (Estes et al., 2013). These demographic trends clearly impact the healthcare industry, which is looking for ways to manage the resulting increased demands for medical care. Not surprisingly, for-profit healthcare enterprises, including stand-alone medical clinics, are on the rise in response to the needs of this burgeoning population (Estes et al., 2013). Chronic conditions prevalent among the elderly are a great example of these healthcare challenges (Estes et al., 2013), leading to increased frequency of visits for monitoring and prevention of adverse outcomes. This can prove costly, which is one reason for the healthcare system's pursuit of effective ways of utilizing technological innovations to provide high quality yet affordable healthcare to our growing population.

The expanded need for healthcare is compounded by the recently passed Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act (ACA), which will increase the number of Americans gaining access to healthcare (Nicholson, 2009). In addition to a growing need

for services, the U.S. healthcare system is burdened by multiple issues such as increased wait times in the primary care setting, financial restraints, and a shortage of primary care physicians. Healthcare reforms currently under discussion anticipate a reduction in the number of uninsured patients by about two-thirds, representing a projected increase of 30 million in the number of insured patients (Nicholson, 2009). The health care reform bill incentivizes health care systems to organize into accountable care organizations (ACOs), focusing on primary care services, coordination of care between providers, and accountability for health outcomes and treatment costs (Nicholson, 2009).

According to the United States Department of Health and Human Services (2013), the demand for primary care physicians is projected to grow by 14%, a need from 27,700 in 2010 to 212,500 in 2020. Compounding this problem, the number of hospital emergency departments (ED) in non-rural areas declined by 27% between 1990 and 2007 (Hellander et al., 2011). As emergency departments frequently provide primary care for patients with limited access to primary care, these ED closures intensify the need for access to low cost affordable quality healthcare.

The ACA was designed to improve access to medical care for people who were not previously accessing care due to lack of healthcare insurance. Healthcare organizations must be positioned to accept increased patient loads, with workable practices and policies in place to manage the increased numbers for both episodic illness and, more importantly, for chronic care (Hellander et al., 2011). Many individuals who previously had no health insurance will be eligible for state-supported insurance. Prior to the ACA, the cost of insurance plans was beyond the means of many middle-income families (Hellander et al., 2011); the average total annual cost of health insurance in 2011

for a family of four by preferred provider plan was approximately \$19,393, an increase of 7.3 percent from 2010 (Hellander et al., 2011). More businesses are now required to provide health insurance to their employees. According to a Price Waterhouse Coopers survey of 1,700 companies, healthcare premiums rose eight and a half percent in 2012, as employers offered their workers only high deductible plans (Hellander et al., 2011). In 2010, Starbucks spent more dollars on healthcare for its U.S. employees than on coffee—in excess of 250 million dollars (Hellander et al., 2011).

Increasing access to primary care has created a need to explore alternatives such as retail health clinics and innovative technological approaches to improve delivery of care. A retail health clinic is based in a pharmacy or other retail setting such as a grocery store or shopping mall. These clinics are staffed by nurse practitioners (NPs) or physician assistants (PAs) and treat episodic common illnesses, perform wellness screenings, and provide vaccinations. These clinics are also referred to as “convenience care” clinics due to the ease of obtaining medical care without an appointment, as well as the short wait times and access to high quality, affordable, evidence-based healthcare.

Telehealth is one approach to increasing healthcare access that is gaining interest across the U.S. and recently being implemented in retail health clinic settings. Telehealth is defined as the use of information and communication technology to facilitate and deliver services to individuals (Rogers et al., 2011) and is seen as a means of providing quality healthcare in a non-traditional manner.

Although telehealth promises to address some of the current issues facing the American healthcare system, it is a relatively recent phenomenon in for-profit primary care settings, with few empirical studies examining the variables which facilitate or

interfere with its implementation. Telehealth is a costly innovation, therefore it is important to understand the factors in the successful adoption of the process, as well as evaluate the differences in execution rates among regions to support further expansion. These variables can be identified by means of an implementation science approach (Proctor et al., 2013). Implementation science is defined as the study of methods that promote the integration of research and evidence into healthcare policy and practice (Proctor et al., 2013). According to Proctor et al. (2013), implementation science seeks to understand the adoption and sustainability of an evidence-based intervention. The approach includes techniques to enhance the adoption, implementation, and sustainability of a clinical program or a practice change (Proctor et al., 2013).

While implementation science explains knowledge transfer, Everett Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations (DOI) theory (Rogers, 2003) provides a conceptual foundation for implementation research (Saint, Howell, & Krein, 2010). DOI theory is a description-oriented model that defines what is occurring within the healthcare setting; however, it does not explain what must be done to implement change (Saint et al., 2010). The Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (PARIHS) framework will also be used as a guide to compliment the DOI theory and is further described below.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to identify the factors that support adoption of telehealth in a retail health clinic setting. The specific characteristics that influence a clinician's adoption of an innovation are important in understanding the acceptance process or facilitation of the innovation, improve workflow, determine the impact on

patient and clinician satisfaction, and improve health outcomes. Both facilitators and barriers to this process are explored in the review of the literature.

Given the current emphasis on limited primary care services, coordination of care among providers, accountability for health outcomes, and cost of treatment, it is prudent to identify new methods of care that may offer innovative solutions. Based on the evidence gathered here, successful implementation strategies can be developed and generalized to other similar settings. The information from the present project may also be utilized for the implementation of telehealth in retail health clinics nationally. Obstacles and late adoption of telehealth were explored in that context. The research question was: “What are the factors that support adoption of telehealth in a retail health clinic?”

Supporting Framework

The PARiHS framework and DOI theory provided the conceptual and theoretical foundations for this project, enabling the author to identify variables associated with the successful implementation of a telehealth innovation. The knowledge gained can be used to support the expansion of telehealth in any health care setting.

PARiHS Conceptual Model

The PARiHS framework was developed by nurse researchers to improve nursing practice and consists of three constructs: evidence, context, and facilitation (Perry et al., 2011). The model suggests that successful implementation of an innovation depends on three characteristics: achievement of the implementation plan, initiation and maintenance of the plan, and attainment of the patient and organizational outcomes (Godzik, 2013). The model elucidates interactions between these three constructs as they relate to

outcome (Figure 1). Successful implementation occurs when the evidence is robust, the context is a receptive one, and the implementation processes are appropriately enabled by facilitators (Godzik, 2013). PARiHS does not predict or explain all behaviors but provides a framework to identify important constructs or variables that influence outcomes. The model has strong validity as a middle-range theory as it has been widely used and cited in international literature. It has been utilized as a tool for both planning and evaluation in optimizing healthcare outcomes.

Figure 1. PARiHS framework conceptualization. Adapted from Helfrich et al., 2010.

The first construct of the PARiHS model identifies sources of evidence from research studies, clinical practice guidelines, and clinical or professional experience that influence implementation and outcomes. In evidence based medicine, research is the most important variable influencing implementation of a healthcare innovation, while noting that other sources of data may also exert some influence (Godzik, 2013).

In the present study, the evidence-based protocols used to guide the implementation of telehealth were standardized across the various clinical settings, based on reviews of the literature and community health standards. These evidence-based protocols allowed for choices of recommended treatment and facilitated discussion with

the patient in relation to previous treatment successes and failures. The current study examined the clinical or professional experience (contributors of evidence) of nurse practitioners (NPs) and Licensed Vocational Nurses (LVNs) for their possible effects on telehealth adoption.

The second element of PARiHS, includes sub-elements of culture, leadership, and evaluation. Culture is most often referred to as “the way things are done around here;” leadership is an indicator of the quality of human relationships in the organization; and evaluation refers to how performance data is generally collected and reported (Helfrich et al., 2010, p. 2). According to Rycroft (2004), leaders such as clinical champions inspire, offer a shared vision, and stimulate and challenge staff thus influencing changes in culture and improve adoption of practice change.

In the present study the culture is characterized by dedication to new innovations and by the extent to which people promote change and growth. The leadership style in this organization is one of partnership and transformation, in which the leadership works with the providers to ensure a team approach. To facilitate telehealth implementation, selected NPs (champions) were trained to consult with patients via telehealth involving a live video feed of a patient session. Champions were selected on the basis of their clinical knowledge, customer satisfaction scores, communication skills, and positive attitude towards innovation. NPs and LVNs were trained to use a debriefing phone call to discuss the telehealth encounter and to evaluate the success or challenges of the consultation. This provided a safe environment in which to suggest improvements in advance of the next visit.

Other important elements of context include the relevance of the innovation to the business, and its managerial fit to its organizational structure. For this clinic, the relevance or purpose of telehealth was twofold. First, the aim was to reduce the number of patients who leave before being seen and second, offer a cost-effective means of utilizing NPs who are not currently providing patient care. “Walk away” visits are counted daily. Reports are generated to measure individual clinics and counties for walk away visits, length of telehealth visits, and to count the total telehealth visits per both LVN and NP.

The third PARiHS construct is facilitation (F), which is the type of support needed to assist clinicians in changing their attitudes or beliefs, skills, or ways of working (Rycroft, 2004). It includes three sub-elements that can influence implementation of practice: personal characteristics, role characteristics, and facilitation style. Facilitation depends on the facilitator who shows others what they need to do or how they need to change in order to achieve the desired outcome—and on their personal characteristics, such as credibility or authenticity. Facilitation can be understood as knowledge translation on a continuum. At the task-oriented end of the continuum, the facilitator’s style is to provide focused help. At the other (holistic) end of the continuum, the facilitator may work on building sustained team relationships to develop change behaviors.

With this project of telehealth implementation, the parent company administration provides team meetings to produce a culture of high achievers. There may be identical training sessions across settings to ensure the desired outcomes of telehealth: exemplary service, more than three telehealth visits per LVN per day, and hands-on practice sessions

to teach familiarity of the environment and equipment. The telehealth equipment provides an extended electronic world with less traditional “touch.” Staff attend training to ease into this new environment and so transform the practice environment.

Diffusion of Innovations Theory

While the PARiHS model explains the process of implementing an innovation, it may not fully account for the variables influencing successful adoption of telehealth. To better understand this phenomenon of interest in the present project, Rogers’ Diffusion of Innovations (DOI) theory was used to explain how and why the rate of adoption spread.

Figure 2. Rogers’ conceptualization of Diffusion of Innovations. Adapted from Berwick, 2003.

Rogers defined diffusion as a process by which an innovation is communicated over time, through certain channels, between members of a social system (Rogers, 2003), and innovation as an idea or practice that is perceived as new by an individual (Rogers, 2003). The theory includes three constructs affecting the spread of a change (Rogers, 2003): perceptions of the innovation, characteristics of people who adopt or fail to adopt

the innovation, and contextual factors that include communication, leadership, management, and incentives (Berwick, 2003).

Innovativeness is defined as the speed with which an individual acts in adopting the new idea as compared to others in the social system (Rogers, 2002). Adopters fall into one of five categories: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards (Figure 2). Innovators are the first 2.5% of the social system to adapt to the innovation, as their interest in new concepts leads them to join groups with pioneering ideas. The next 13.5 % are early adopters, who are looked to by leaders for their opinions and who can speed up the innovation process. A chasm or gap that occurs between innovators and early adopters is referred to as the gap between knowledge and practice, also described as a failure to use available science (Berwick, 2003). Early majority adopters constitute the next 34%, followed by the late majority who are the following 34%. Finally, the laggards represent the final 16%, who only adapt to the new idea because they are surrounded by peers who have already accepted it (Rogers, 2002).

During this adoption process, the characteristics that determine the rate of adoption are *relative advantage*, *trialability*, *complexity*, *observability*, and *compatibility* (Menachemi et al., 2004). These are defined in the review of the literature and serve as the foundation for this section of the project. At the onset of this study, there was lack of evidence concerning which variables would optimize telehealth implementation in the project setting.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

The relevant literature for telehealth as an alternative method of delivery of care encompasses a variety of studies across a range of settings (see Appendix A). With the implementation of the ACA, it was appropriate to review studies that look at the importance of alternate interventions assisting the delivery of care during the current healthcare crisis. Additionally, several countries with a longer history of telehealth provision illustrated the strengths and weaknesses of this delivery system and were therefore of relevance here. As a modern innovation, telehealth provision presents a unique set of challenges for both healthcare providers and patients. It was important to understand these challenges, including the specifics of facilitators and barriers to telehealth adoption, for analysis and adaptation in future innovations of this nature.

The inclusion criteria for the literature review were as follows: (a) related to the topics of telehealth, diffusion of innovations theory, PARIHS framework, successful adopters of innovation, or retail health clinics; (b) English language; and (c) relevant to the relationships being studied. An online search of PubMed, CINAHL, Cochrane, and Google Scholar was performed, using the search terms *telehealth*, *implementation science*, *diffusion of innovations theory*, *PARIHS framework*, *successful adopters of an innovation*, and *retail health clinics*. The dates searched were 2000–2014. The MESH terms for this project included telehealth, implementation science, PARIHS framework, diffusion of innovations theory, early and late adopters of an innovation, barriers to innovations, and retail health clinics.

DOI theory was especially helpful when synthesizing the evidence related to the implementation of telehealth. In his landmark textbook *Diffusion of Innovations*, Everett Rogers, 2003 defined three basic concepts that influence the spread of change: perceptions of the innovation; characteristics of people who either adopt or fail to adopt the innovation; and contextual factors that include communication, leadership, management, and incentives (Rogers, 2003). This review of the literature also includes a discussion of key adopter groups as resistance from any one of these could affect implementation of telehealth. These adopter groups, also identified within the PARIHS framework, were clinicians, patients, and administrators.

Perceptions of Innovation

Perceptions of an innovation by individuals within the social system is the most powerful factor influencing change (Rogers, 2003). According to Rogers (2003), individual perceptions can affect change acceptance by anything from 49% to 87%. Rogers' further writings on DOI theory identified characteristics that determine an innovation's rate of adoption; these are relative advantage, trialability, complexity, observability, and compatibility (Menachemi et al., 2004).

Relative Advantage

This refers to the degree to which an innovation is perceived as better than or complementary to the current way of doing things (Menachemi et al., 2004). Many studies have found a relationship between relative advantage and facilitation of telemedicine (Garrett, Hocking, Chen, Fairley, & Kirkman, 2011; Moeckli, Cram, Cunningham, & Schacht-Reisinger, 2013; Rahimpour, Lovel, Celler, & McCormick, 2007; Rogers, Kirk, Gately, May, & Finch, 2011; Smith, 2005).

Cost reduction is an important factor influencing relative advantage. Cost savings and efficient allocation of resources achieved through telehealth can frequently generate additional revenues (Rahimpour et al., 2007; Rogers et al., 2011; Smith, 2005). However, the converse is also true; the investment cost of equipment and staff training may also influence the decision makers involved in an innovation. One mixed methods study by Smith (2005) focused on the financial considerations associated with implementing telemedicine. A convenience sample included seventeen participants from the disciplines of administration, clinical, and information technology at four non-profit hospitals in the United States (U.S.). The results suggest that financial burden is a major barrier for all decision makers and reimbursement is the largest concern for long-term sustainability. Other barriers to adoption were patient and physician acceptance, technical knowledge to make the project functional, and resistance to implementation. The barrier of fear about adequacy of financial resources was similar across all three disciplines. Providers believed that organizations could implement small telemedicine projects but were reluctant to extend to bigger projects because of concerns about cost.

Trialability

Reluctance to implement telehealth may also be influenced by trialability—the extent to which the proposed adopter believes they can find a way of testing change on a smaller scale before it is implemented on a larger scale (Berwick, 2003; Smith, 2005).

Trialability, cost reduction, and quality of care were key factors in a study by Rahimpour et al. (2007), which examined factors that influenced patients' perceptions of a Home Telecare Management System (HTMS) in Australia. Using a Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) framework, they wanted to improve success of

implementation and to identify acceptance factors. A study sample of seventy-seven participants included patients with either congestive heart failure (CHF) or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Ten focus groups of multiethnic diversity watched video demonstrations of HTMS usage and participants were questioned on its usage. Of these, 64% reported a positive attitude and showed an intention to use the HTMS. They felt that it helped them to know their body better, that it was convenient, and that the interaction gave them peace of mind. Patients' knowledge of their health status empowered them to improve daily self-care and compliance with medical treatments. The barriers to HTMS were confidentiality, technological support, cost, and increased learning time for elderly patients. A major positive outcome was the healthcare delivery impact of decreased ER and hospital admissions. Uniquely, this study identified a new barrier (HTMS anxiety) and a new facilitator (self-efficacy), both of which the researchers recommended for inclusion in future theoretical frameworks.

Self-efficacy refers to the individual's ability or self-sufficiency in utilizing the HTMS monitoring equipment (Rahimpour et al., 2007). This is an important concept in relative advantage, as the more knowledge an individual can gain about the expected consequence of an innovation, the more likely it is that they will understand and be influenced by it (Berwick, 2003; Rahimpour et al., 2007). According to Rogers' DOI theory, the greater the reduction in uncertainty, the more likely it is that an individual will adopt a change (Berwick, 2003).

In another study with similar findings on the importance of self-efficacy and cost reduction, Rogers et al. (2011) focused on the social practices of telecare ideas, three themes emerged: 1) integrating and adapting to telecare systems takes time and

adjustment to bulky and intrusive equipment; 2) the impact of telecare on existing illness takes time as both patient and healthcare professional adjust to a daily routine; and 3) when utilizing health services, patients felt self-monitoring made them less of a burden, as there was less reliance on staff in reducing flare-ups and hospitalizations. The results showed relative advantage in policies designed to support the use of telecare for presumed gains, as the patient's self-reliance and responsibility increased when motivated through regular monitoring. This would save cost on bed days. The authors recommended that policy makers need to look at alternatives to traditional visits in meeting current healthcare needs, focusing on the human aspect of self-care provision as a resource in cost reduction.

Complexity

Coupled with the theme of self-care and self-efficacy, there is evidence that elderly adopters of telehealth may seek to avoid the novelty and unfamiliarity of change placing an extra burden of proof on the innovation (Chun & Patterson, 2012; Rogers et al., 2011). According to implementation science, complexity is the third main factor affecting the rate of diffusion of innovations (Menachemi et al., 2004; Rogers, 2003). While equipment tends to work as it should, many users may find the equipment more complex and sophisticated than expected (Berwick, 2003).

A mixed methods study by Chun and Patterson (2012) explored the differences between younger and older patients in their responses to Internet-based telemedicine in a program based in the Department of Industrial Engineering at Texas Tech University. In a study of 16 patients using an Internet-based program called My Health Vet, participants completed eight electronic tasks within a 200-second time limit. Task examples included

logging into a healthcare website, finding their previous medication list, or finding information on healthy eating. The participants completed a 21-item survey, including two open-ended questions. The results showed that older adults completed 64 % of the tasks but had more difficulty in working out where to click, and spent longer thinking about their next move. Younger adults completed 80% of the tasks, processed information faster, and made less purposeful clicks. One observed barrier was that decisions about where to click were challenging for older adults in the absence of any obvious or direct clue and access to terms and definitions was helpful in this regard. The researchers noted that both organization and structure were important facilitators in designing tools for seniors. This concept of tailoring the tool for the user is also important in the following arena, where user compatibility is important.

Compatibility

The fourth main attribute of diffusion innovation is compatibility, defined as the degree to which the innovation is compatible with the beliefs, past history, and current needs of the individual (Menachemi et al., 2004; Rogers, 2003). Compatibility can be operationalized as either a barrier or a facilitator for adoption of an innovation such as telehealth. In contrast to the study described by Chun and Patterson (2012), Garrett et al., (2009) found that younger people were less receptive to telehealth as a belief system. This is negative compatibility, where the user may not feel comfortable with the new technology or with being diagnosed by a clinician far away, as this has not been part of their prior belief system (Menachemi et al., 2004). Menachemi et al. (2004) described the negative compatibility (some authors would identify this as a barrier) experienced by young people wishing to access sexual health services via telemedicine. This study,

conducted in Australia, included convenience sampling of 662 participants, who were asked in an online questionnaire about their willingness to use media communication for medical consultations relating to sexual health. The results showed that 85% of the sample would be willing to have an in-person consultation with a doctor, 63% would be willing to have a telephone consultation, and 29% would be willing to have a webcam consultation. The most prominent facilitator was time savings and convenience. If the clinic was 20 minutes away or less, 83% would have preferred an in-person consultation. The largest observed barrier was privacy; the researchers anticipated that more people would be comfortable with a sexual consultation via media communication if medical companies could reduce concerns about privacy and security. Interestingly, although it may be assumed from previous studies that younger patients are more compatible or adapt more quickly to electronic equipment, the majority of younger patients in this study did not mind the barrier of a 20-minute commute to attend a face-to-face visit (Menachemi et al., 2004).

The literature suggests that telehealth is considered a viable alternative to traditional face-to-face medical care (Gagnon, Duplantie, Fortin, & Landry, 2007; Garrett et al., 2011; Moeckli, Cram, Cunningham, & Schacht-Reisinger, 2013; Rahimpour et al., 2007). In one such study, Gagnon et al. (2007) explored the effects of telehealth on medical human resources in remote regions. They identified seven recruitment and retention factors for compatibility of users: family, community, lifestyle, professional, economic, educational, and organizational. The sample consisted of 63 healthcare workers from different disciplines. Data from semi-structured interviews revealed a shortage of medical resources in many countries. The authors found compatibility with

telehealth use only if the following three criteria were met: improvement of services, improvement of patient well-being, and innovation as an asset for recruitment and retention. This study provides an insight into potential future human resource issues related to telehealth. It also highlights barriers such as technology integration and organizational misfit; if the innovation is not compatible with the organizational mission, it is likely to be a misfit (Berwick, 2003; Menachemi et al., 2004).

In terms of compatibility, a unified and well-understood vision, shared by both management and users is necessary for successful adoption of a telemedicine initiative. A study by Postema, Peeters, and Friele (2001) explored implementation of home telecare within care organizations, to determine which factors facilitate or impede successful implementation. The researchers sampled 27 participants from three home care organizations in the Netherlands, and five themes were identified: stability of the innovation, financing, telehealth as a complement to physical care, top management support from the outset, and homogeneity of implementation strategy goals. The major underlying facilitator in this study was that management supported the use of video communication. The literature further supports the view that if administrators and local management are supportive of the innovation, then their teams are more likely to adapt to it (Berwick, 2003; Gagnon et al., 2007; Menachemi et al., 2004; Postema et al., 2001). For example, if the management team is concerned with cost reduction within the healthcare setting, and telehealth presents a viable way of achieving this, administrators are more likely to consider such an innovation as compatible with their needs.

Observability

A less prominent element in DOI theory but also of importance, observability is the ease with which adopters can watch others trying to change. This is most apparent where the perceived benefits of telehealth are more applicable to certain groups of medical providers than to others (Berwick, 2003; Menachemi et al., 2004). The benefit of observability is most often seen among certain types of specialists, such as radiologists, who use high technology equipment. For that reason, it was surprising that Moeckli et al. (2013) found evidence of negative compatibility in intensive care units, which routinely utilize high technology equipment such as remote cardiac monitoring. Exploring key factors influencing telecare in an intensive care (ICU) setting, the purpose was to explore acceptance of a telecare ICU program at pre-implementation and post-implementation. The sample included eight ICUs at seven facilities that varied in structural and organizational characteristics. The tele-ICU team of clinicians, based at a different geographic location, included one intensivist and two critical care nurses. Individual, semi-structured interviews and site observations were conducted with staff from the Veteran's Affairs (VA) Healthcare network and affiliates. This was the pilot for tele-ICU programs to be implemented in three integrated VA service networks. Interviews were conducted at one to three weeks and six to twelve weeks after implementation. Interview guides were used to assess staff perceptions, expectations, and attitudes toward tele-ICU. The results suggest that staff acceptance of tele-ICU was influenced by tele-ICU training, understanding and expectations of innovation, perceived need for innovation, and organizational factors. The authors concluded that tele-ICU could be very disruptive to workflow patterns.

Barriers identified in this study included confusion regarding equipment use, communication disruptions, unmet expectations, and feelings of being monitored. The lack of perceived need among staff for the innovation was also a barrier and the authors recommended that healthcare settings considering a telehealth innovation should allocate resources to education and systematic change. Despite evidence that telehealth can improve outcomes through expedited care (Gagnon et al., 2007; Garret et al., 2011; Moeckli et al., 2013; Rahimpour et al., 2007; Rogers et al., 2011), the addition of remote monitoring was not welcomed in this critical care unit.

This literature review suggests that the full potential of telehealth has yet to be realized. Apprehension is the main barrier to adoption of this kind of innovation. Other concerns include cost, knowledge deficits or preconceived ideas in user ability, intrusive nature of equipment, confidentiality, and organizational misfit. The main facilitators of adoption are cost savings and patient self-efficacy. Other facilitators that can positively influence rate of adoption are reduced disease process, reduced long-term health burden, increased healthcare access in rural areas, and organizational support. It is interesting that many of the barriers can in some cases be facilitators. Although the literature does not address implementation of telehealth in a retail health setting, the available evidence suggests that DOI theory's constructs of relative advantage, trialability, complexity, observability, and compatibility, influence the successful implementation of innovations such as telehealth.

METHODS

A cross-sectional design using an online survey was employed to address the aims of the project (see Appendix C). Data was collected from nurses (NP or LVN) employed at retail health clinics in four regions in southern California from the fall of 2013 to the fall of 2014. The corporation at which the participants were employed sent an email invitation to all eligible nurses, containing a link to the online survey. The participants completed the survey at their places of employment within a fifteen-day time period and had the option to exit the survey at any time. No personal identifiers were linked to the survey.

The online survey was created with Qualtrics® software after a review of related literature, which identified the key factors associated with the adoption of an innovation (Menachemi, Burke, & Ayres, 2004; Northouse, 2013). Benbasat et al. provided permission to adapt the survey and include the term “telehealth.” The survey consisted of 36 items and included an informed consent question, and took approximately 10 minutes to complete (see Appendix C). The survey included questions related to the participants’ characteristics, items reflecting the Diffusion of Innovations theory (relative advantage, compatibility, trialability, observability, and complexity) and three open-ended questions (statements on training, feelings on NP/ LVN interactions, and any additional thoughts). These open-ended questions were utilized for the description of thoughts and feelings that may not have been addressed in the standardized tool and which may have affected implementation of telehealth. The Cronbach’s Alpha for the construct section of the survey ($\alpha = 0.862$) compared favorably with that reported in the literature (α varied from 0.71-0.92; Moore & Benbasat, 2014).

Independent Variables

The independent variables for this project reflect the constructs of Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Theory (relative advantage, compatibility, trialability, observability, and complexity), as well as the constructs identified by Moore and Benbasat (2014) of voluntariness, visibility, and ease of use. Examples of questions from the survey include: "I was permitted to use telehealth on a trial basis long enough to see what it could do" (trialability), "I think that using telehealth fits well with the way I like to work" (compatibility), and "Overall, I believe that telehealth is easy to use" (complexity). The survey also included three open-ended questions assessing perceptions of telehealth training, the collegial relationship between LVNs and NPs, and any other thoughts that the nurses wished to share. The responses to these questions were reviewed by the author and common themes were identified. Demographic information that was likely to influence the adoption of an innovation, as identified from the literature (Moeckli et al., 2013) was also collected (years of experience, months of prior telehealth experience, and professional roles). Other standard demographic information about age, sex, and the home clinic was not collected in order to protect the participants' anonymity.

Outcome Variables

The outcome variable (telehealth adoption) was created from the data provided by the corporation employing the nurses. The corporation provided the number of actual telehealth visits, or adoptions (numerator), and the total number of clinic visits, or potential adoption visits (denominator). This metric was created to describe the extent of telehealth adoption (metric/data not shown). Regions A and B (incorporates two areas under the same management) displayed similar metrics and were designated the high-

adopter regions, whereas regions C and D (two areas under different management), which also exhibited similar metrics, were designated the low-adopter regions. These two groups were compared with each other. The telehealth adoption data was aggregated at the county level to ensure the confidentiality of the participants.

Analysis

The Statistical Analysis System for Windows, version 9.3 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, N.C.) was used for statistical analyses. The Likert-scale items were collapsed to Agree/Strongly Agree versus Neutral/Disagree/Strongly Disagree in order to stabilize cell size. Measures of central tendency (e.g., frequencies, means, and standard deviations) were calculated to describe the baseline characteristics of the participants, as well as to measure other responses to the survey. Bivariate statistics (Chi-Square, Fisher's Exact test, and ANOVA F test) were used to examine the associations between the independent variables and the adoption of telehealth. High- and low-adopter groups were stratified and a *p* value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

Sixty-three nurses completed the survey, giving a response rate of 68%. On average, the respondents had 10.5 years in practice. Seventy-six percent were NPs and 24% were LVNs (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Respondent's Professional Role in the Organization.

Forty-three percent of respondents worked in high-adoption counties. High adopters and low adopters did not differ in levels of education ($p = 0.592$), the time it took for respondents to answer the survey ($p = 0.329$), years in practice ($p = 0.054$), and months' use of telehealth at baseline ($p = 0.913$). Seventy seven percent of the respondents had a Bachelor's degree or higher with the remaining having education at the Associate Degree or Licensed Vocational Nursing Degree level (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Respondent's level of education.

Sixty percent of respondents rated the quality of care delivered via telehealth as very effective (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Survey Question 12: How would you describe the quality of care delivered via Telehealth to patients in your clinic?

The results of the individual survey questions are displayed in Table B1 (see Appendix B). Further discussion of the significant constructs are discussed below and illustrated in the bivariate Table 1.

Two questions examining the construct of voluntariness were significant. The first asked, “My boss requires me to use telehealth,” in which 42.3% of high telehealth adopters and 8.1% of low telehealth adopters answered Strongly Agree or Agree ($\chi^2 = 10.333$; $p = 0.002$); and the second asked, “Although it might be helpful, using telehealth is compulsory in my job,” in which 53.8% of high telehealth adopters and 5.4% of low telehealth adopters answered affirmatively ($\chi^2 = 18.911$; $p < .0001$).

Two items measuring the compatibility construct were significantly associated with telehealth adoption. The first item asked, “I think that using telehealth fits well with the way I like to work,” in which 88.5% of high telehealth adopters answered affirmatively versus 62.2% of low telehealth adopters ($\chi^2 = 5.360$; $p = 0.024$); and the second item asked, “Using telehealth fits into my work style,” in which 88.5% of high telehealth adopters and 59.5% of low telehealth adopters answered affirmatively ($\chi^2 = 6.294$; $p = 0.022$). The bivariate results are displayed in Table 1. No other differences between the constructs for the high and low adopters were noted to be significant. The average number of months on telehealth was 10.6 for both adopter groups (see Table 1).

Table 1

Bivariate Analysis of Telehealth Questionnaire and Demographic Characteristics (n = 63)

Question	Telehealth Adopters		χ^2 ^a	P ^{a,b}
	High (n = 26; 41.3%)	Low (n = 37; 58.7%)		
Q2_1 (Voluntariness - My boss requires me to use Telehealth)				
Agree ¹	11 (42.3)	3 (8.1)	10.3332	0.0020 ^a
Disagree ²	15 (57.7)	34 (91.9)		
Q2_2 (Voluntariness - Although it might be helpful, using Telehealth is compulsory in my job)				
Agree ¹	14 (53.8)	2 (5.4)	18.9112	<.0001 ^a
Disagree ²	12 (46.2)	35 (94.6)		
Q4_2 (Compatibility - I think that using Telehealth fits well with the way I like to work)				
Agree ¹	23 (88.5)	23 (62.2)	5.3604	0.0239 ^b
Disagree ²	3 (11.5)	14 (37.8)		
Q4_3 (Compatibility - Using Telehealth fits into my work style)				
Agree ¹	23 (88.5)	22 (59.5)	6.2935	0.0219 ^b
Disagree ²	3 (11.5)	15 (40.5)		
Education 3				
Bachelors/Masters/Doctorate	21 (80.8)	27 (75.0)	0.2874	0.5919 ^a
LVN/LPN/Associate/Other	5 (19.2)	9 (25.0)		
Time (min.) it took				
Respondents to answer Survey	9.9 ± 8.2	16.4 ± 20.7	1.13 ^c	0.3295 ^c
$\bar{x} \pm s$	6.6-13.3	9.5-23.3		
95% CI	3-34; 1.6	3-71, 3.4		
Range, SE				
Years in practice				
$\bar{x} \pm s$	11.9 ± 11.8	9.2 ± 8.5	3.08 ^c	0.0544
95% CI	6.9-16.9	6.1-12.2		
Range, SE	1-40, 2.4	1-36, 1.0		
Months used Telehealth				
$\bar{x} \pm s$	12.9 ± 2.9	12.5 ± 9.4	0.09 ^c	0.9131 ^c
95% CI	11.7-14.1	9.2-15.8		
Range, SE	1-18, 0.6	1-60, 1.6		

Notes. High Telehealth Adopters (Regions A & B); Low Telehealth Adopters (Regions C & D).

¹Agree = Agree/Strongly Agree categories were collapsed; ²Disagree = Neutral/Disagree/Strongly Disagree were collapsed; \bar{x} = sample mean; s = sample standard deviation; 3n = 36; ^aChi-Square Test; ^bPearson's Exact Chi-Square Test; ^cANOVA (One-Way) F test.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this project was to identify the factors associated with adoption of telehealth in a retail health-clinic setting. It is important to understand the characteristics that influence adoption and facilitate innovation because this information can be used to support future innovations that could improve the delivery of healthcare. This project identifies potential targets for managers to consider when improving telehealth adoption.

In this investigation, two questions related to the construct of voluntariness were significantly associated with telehealth adoption. For the question, “Although it might be helpful, using telehealth is compulsory in my job,” there was a ten-fold difference between high adopters and low adopters ($\chi^2 = 18.911, p < .0001$). For the question, “My boss requires me to use telehealth,” the high adopters were five times as likely to agree with this statement as the low adopters. Clearly, there was a difference between high and low adopters in the views related to voluntariness.

The construct of voluntariness is based on the assumption that adoption could be viewed either as voluntary or compulsory, and that there may be a higher adoption rate if a person is free to choose whether to use it or not (Rogers, 2002). In this sample, all of the nurses were informed that telehealth was a mandatory requirement for employment. However, 91.9% of the low adopters believed it to be “voluntary” rather than mandatory. Freedom of choice provides the adopter with control and the desire, therefore, to achieve success.

Furthermore, the company may “expect” an employee to use an innovation, but the employee’s perception may be that it is “voluntary,” as the example above shows. The fact that the company believes it to be compulsory does not ensure that the employee

will view it in the same way, in other words. In addition, the literature suggests that voluntariness may be perceived differently by individuals of certain social statuses, which may depend on one's professional role within an organization (Moore & Benbasat, 2014; Rogers, 2003). For example, in this sample, the LVNs in regions A and B were asked to maintain a minimum of three telehealth visits per shift during the initial implementation. Many exceeded this minimum, leading this area to become a high-adopter region.

To improve the adoption of telehealth in the future, it is important to identify strategies to improve perceived voluntariness. One suggestion is to have managers regularly visiting low-adoption clinics to ensure that telehealth is being offered to all of the appropriate patients, as per company protocols. Due to the logistical constraints that managers face, however, they might consider appointing telehealth champions—both LVNs and NPs—who excel in the operation of telehealth (based on excellent customer service scores and on practice in a high-adoption region).

According to Bradshaw and Lowenstein (2014), students respond best to clinicians who exhibit passion for their work, including commitment, trust, collaboration, caring, and achievement. Champions could be assigned to oversee and spend extra time in low-adopter clinics, offering expert support, answering questions, and providing encouragement in relation to the challenges clinicians may be experiencing. This support may reduce the burdens associated with the stress of a new innovation. Research suggests that peer interactions (with champions) may influence adoption; in particular, role play can be used to provide immediate feedback to learners in a nonthreatening environment, allowing them to improve their interpersonal skills (Bradshaw & Lowenstein, 2014). Peer review is another system of partnership in the learning process. This form of critiquing is

another effective way to facilitate cooperative learning as it allows for the discovery and correction of inadequacies (Loke & Chow, 2007). For low adopters, a discussion including “a lack of adherence to expected company outcomes” and a plan with personal performance-improvement goals can be created to encourage adoption.

In this project, two items reflecting compatibility were statistically associated with telehealth adoption. Both of these questions reflect an individual’s perception that telehealth is consistent with their needs, current existing beliefs or values, and past experiences (Rogers, 2002). Although these quantitative results yielded a negative compatibility, the qualitative responses (discussed below) showed the opposite. Low adopters were three times as likely to disagree with the statement ($\chi^2 = 5.360, p = 0.024$), “I think that using telehealth fits well with the way I like to work,” and four times as likely to disagree with the statement, “Using telehealth fits into my work style,” as high adopters.

The free-text questions provided insight into other aspects of compatibility. The perceived loss of patient contact that occurs with telehealth was viewed as a barrier to adoption. Several nurses stated that they felt patient interaction was compromised during a visit. However, in a telehealth visit, the patient becomes an active participant in their care, thus improving interactions and communication. When the patient is able to visualize his/her own disease process via pictures, numbers, or trends on a screen, s/he may become more visually aware of his/her own health, and this may improve adherence to their treatment regimen (Rogers et al., 2011). This can increase both clinicians’ and patients’ satisfaction, as well as reducing the health-care dollars spent.

In addition, the free-text responses help to give an understanding of the link between relationships and telehealth adoption. Numerous responses to the question “Describe your thoughts about the NP and LVN interaction” were positive. The relationship between NPs and LVNs was described as “a professional collaboration which drives the visit to be smooth, efficient and effective.” Other respondents stated that the “collaborative team work[s] to provide the best care to our patients,” and “the interaction between NPs and LVNs is cohesive and pleasant.” Although the issue of interpersonal collaboration between nurses may not reflect the construct of compatibility in its purest definition, human collaboration is critical for successful telehealth implementation and optimal patient outcomes. The NPs had worked independently within the study setting (the clinics) since their opening eight years ago. The LVNs were hired approximately 18 months previously.

Within the qualitative data, a few responses suggested that the participants may perceive issues with telehealth’s compatibility with their work style, as they prefer face-to-face patient visits. One nurse wrote, “As an NP, I found that I prefer the face-to-face office visit . . . [the hands on compassion of physical interaction is important. For example] the patient’s illness is validated with a handshake, pat on back, or eye to eye [all of which can be a] reassurance to amazing care.” Other respondents wrote, “Although telehealth is great technology, it should not be used [since someone else is] examining the patient on your behalf . . . [but it is not equivalent to] having performed the exam yourself [since you are] . . . documenting on blind faith,” and “This mode of seeing patients is effective . . . if this is the only way . . . an in-person interaction is better.”

The negative responses reflect the participants' views on the compatibility of telehealth with the existing day-to-day operations of the retail health clinic.

In order to better understand the influence of compatibility on telehealth adoption in this project, a sensitivity analysis was undertaken to examine the length of time it took high adopters and low adopters to complete the study. The high-adopter group took an average of 9.9 minutes to complete the survey, versus 16.4 minutes for low adopters of telehealth. The fact that low adopters took 66% longer to complete the survey raises some questions about the possibility that low adopters may be slower when it comes to technology usage. It is also important to note that both groups of respondents may have completed the survey during patient care time and that they had the option to pause the survey and to complete it after caring for a patient.

There are many aspects of telehealth that may make it compatible with a variety of personal work styles. For example, the research suggests that proper telehealth equipment provides physical examination views that are equivalent, if not better, than face-to-face visits (Menachemi et al., 2004.) Since clinicians generally seek optimum patient-care experiences, they may view this healthcare delivery system, therefore, as a suitable method for performing a physical examination. In the findings of this study, 83% percent of the participants answered the quality question, "How would you describe the quality of care delivered via telehealth?" with the responses either "very effective" or "effective."

Another potential factor that supports compatibility with work flow is the method by which telehealth is implemented across a region. In one set of regions (both high-adopter regions) NPs were allowed to provide telehealth to consecutive patients without

having to provide face-to-face care as well as telehealth care. In two other regions (both low-adopter regions) the NPs provide face-to-face visits and telehealth visits concurrently. This ability of the NPs in the high-adopter regions to focus directly on telehealth visits may give them an advantage over those in the low-adopter regions. However, the LVNs in all of the regions routinely manage both face-to-face visits and telehealth visits.

Additional Considerations with Telehealth Adoption

In this project, the items reflecting relative advantage, image, ease of use, result demonstrability, trialability, visibility, professional role, and quality of care were not statistically associated with the adoption of telehealth. However, it is important to consider that a lack of statistical significance does not equate to a lack of clinical importance when facilitating telehealth adoption in the future. DOI theory suggests that all of these constructs influence the successful implementation of innovations such as telehealth (Rogers, 2003).

Limitations

Although these results provide valuable information for directing future quality improvement projects to improve the adoption of telehealth, several limitations exist. The sample size in this project was small, potentially leading to spurious results. Statistical significance was found for four items, suggesting that a type II error was unlikely. The need to protect individual participant anonymity prevented the study from focusing on specific clinics, and data collection was aggregated at the county level. However, several factors differed between the high-adopter and low-adopter regions, which provides organizational information when considering future telehealth implementation strategies,

such as interventions to improve interpersonal compatibility between LVNs and NPs, and interventions so that telehealth can be used to improve the day-to-day work flow.

The high-adopter regions (regions A and B) were grouped together but actually represent two distinct geographic regions. In the future, a wider geography may be necessary in order to better understand telehealth adoption. Another limitation is the potential for selection bias. Unfortunately, no data was available in relation to the non-responders to this project. However, the response rate was especially robust for an online survey.

Cross-sectional study designs offer only a “snap shot” of a phenomenon and may not be representative of an evolving process such as telehealth implementation (Polit & Beck, 2012). Exposure and outcomes cannot be studied temporally and it is impossible to infer causality (Polit & Beck, 2012). Yet, the findings from this project translate to other innovations, especially related to the implementation of technology to improve healthcare.

CONCLUSION

The Diffusion of Innovations theory suggests that early adopters have more positive perceptions of innovations than the non-adopters (Rogers, 2002). Since diffusion is a process by which an innovation is communicated through certain channels over time among members of a social system, the messages being communicated require attention (Rogers, 2002). This diffusion or spread of messages also introduces an element of uncertainty both to the individuals and the organization as they must digest new ideas that represent proposed innovations. Innovations spread at different rates and it is the characteristics of an innovation, as perceived by the individuals in the social system, that truly influence the rate of adoption.

In this project, the idea that it is an individual's choice to utilize telehealth, despite the company's expectation, was a strong predictor of adoption. It is important to recognize the construct of compatibility in order to continue to nurture team support (between the LVNs and NPs) and to monitor the compatibility of work flow.

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APPENDIX A

TABLES OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Summary of Evidence for Mixed Methods Studies

Purpose (Author/s, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements; Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Explore differences in internet based telemedicine in younger vs. older patients. (Chun & Patterson, 2012)	Mixed methods—both computerized task-taking and post-test questionnaire. Ease of using Interface—“My Health Vet”. Ages: Younger adults (average age 27 y/o) <i>n</i> = 10 Older adults: (average age 61 y/o) <i>n</i> = 6.	<i>N</i> = 16. Dept. of Industrial Engineering at Texas Tech University.	Participants completed 8 electronic tasks within a 200-seconds time limit. Task examples: log into a healthcare website; find your previous medication list; find information on healthy eating.	Older adults had more difficulty inferring where to click to the next step, spending more time thinking about next move, longer task completion, 64% of tasks done. Younger adults made more errors on less purposeful clicks, faster information processing, 80% of tasks done.	Decisions on where to click are challenging for older adults when there is no direct or obvious cue on the homepage. Having definitions of terms available proved helpful. Organization and structure are important in designing tools for seniors.
Financial considerations in implementing telemedicine. (Smith, 2005)	Mixed methods. Reasons influencing telemedicine implementation.	<i>N</i> = 17. Purposive convenience sample from administrative, clinical, financial, technology disciplines.	Task questionnaire created by authors; 5-point Likert scale: 21 multiple choice and open-ended questions. Questionnaire of 5 financial questions and 5-point Likert scale, open-ended questions.	15 interviews, each lasting 1-1.5 hrs. Financial burden is a major concern for decision makers in both rural and urban areas; reimbursement is largest barrier to long-term sustainability.	Providers believe that reimbursement is the largest barrier to long-term sustainability. Concerns for financial resources similar between disciplines.

4 not-for-profit hospital systems in southeastern region of US.	Interview for perceptions of experience.	Other concerns: patient and physician acceptance, technical knowledge to make project functional, resistance to implementation.	Organizations will implement small telemedicine projects, but are reluctant to expand.
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Note: TC = Telecare; D/C = discontinue; HTMS = Home Telecare Management System; MED = multiethnic diversity as described by Multicultural Health Unit experts from Sydney, Australia: Anglo/Celtic, Italian, Chinese, Assyrian, Russian, Greek, and South Pacific Islander; FGI = Focus Group Interviews; TAM = Technology Acceptance Model; PT = patient; R/T = related to; M = male; F = female; PARiHS = Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services; MAXQDA = software program designed for computers; IRB = Institutional Review Board; VISN = Veterans Integrated Service Networks; CCRN = Critical Care Registered Nurse.

Summary of Evidence for Qualitative Studies

Purpose (Author/s, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements; Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Exploring factors influencing implementation in home telecare in care organizations. (Postema et al, 2011).	Phenomena of interest: 1. Success of home telecare in care organizations 2. Perceptions of factors affecting implementation success.	<i>N</i> = 27. Convenience sample. 3 home care organizations in The Netherlands. Stakeholders: 1. Board members, RN, caregivers 2. Technology providers, health insurers.	Semi-structured topic guides, sessions recorded and transcribed for use in MAXQDA; 2 Researchers extrapolated data by means of qualitative analysis; categories were compared and synthesized.	Implementation of evaluation framework—Fleuren: 5 factors facilitate or impede success: Innovation, socio-political context, characteristics of adopting persons and organization, implementation strategy 1. Stability critical 2. Financing is a major influence 3. Virtual assistance complements physical care 4. Top management support at outset 5. Implementation strategy—goals need homogeneity.	Major theme: management support critical for success of video communication.
Exploring key factors that affect patients' perceptions of a HTMS. (Rahimpour et al., 2007).	Phenomena of interest: 1. Patients' perceptions of home TC 2. Human aspects of the technology; innovation to increase usefulness, improve success 3. Identify acceptance factors based on TAM framework.	<i>N</i> = 77. Sydney, Australia; patients with CHF and/or COPD.	10 focus groups of multi-ethnic diversity, (MED). Participants watched video demo of HTMS usage and were questioned on their perceptions of its usage; discussions audiotaped, with use of large written discussion boards in their own language.	64 % response rate; group size ranged from 6–12. Ages: 50–90 y/o, mean and median age 71 y/o. 1. Intention to use: positive attitude towards HTMS, knew body better; usefulness—most PT thought convenient, less time consuming, peace of mind 2. Impact on PT health: knowledge of health status	Most findings consistent with previous home TC studies. Identification of 2 new variables—HTMS anxiety and self- efficacy—that should be included in future theoretical frameworks. Limitations: geographic area (Australia only),

				empowers PT to improve daily self-care/compliance 3. Concerns: HTMS confidentiality, tech support, cost, more learning time for elderly 4. Delivery impact-less ER/admissions.	should include other areas and MED.
Phenomenological study exploring key factors influencing ICU telecare in intensive care settings. (Moeckli et al., 2013).	Phenomena of interest: Factors related to ICU acceptance of a telecare ICU (tele-ICU) program in pre- and post-implementation phases.	$N = 8$ ICUs. Included 8 ICUs at 7 facilities—varied in structural & organizational characteristics. Tele-ICU: clinician team was located remotely and included 1 intensivist, 2 CCRNs; VA pilot for tele-ICU programs implemented in 3 VA integrated service networks (VISN) in Minneapolis, Omaha, and Iowa City.	Individual and group semi-structured interviews and site observations were conducted with staff from VA Midwest Healthcare Network and affiliates. Interviews conducted 1–3 weeks before implementation, and 6–12 weeks after tele-ICU implementation; Interview guides used to assess staff perceptions, expectations and attitudes to tele-ICU. Codebook developed based on <i>a priori</i> research questions.	Staff acceptance of tele-ICU influenced by: 1. Tele-ICU training 2. Tele-ICU understanding and expectations 3. Perceived need for innovation 4. Organizational factors in acceptance of telecare.	Implementation of telehealth in ICU can be very disruptive; expanded virtual care team requires acceptance to avoid complicating workflow. Barriers included confusion regarding equipment use, communication disruptions, unmet expectations, feeling of being monitored. Hospitals considering this implementation must allocate substantial resources to education and systematic change.
Consideration of the social practices of the work of TC integration and incorporation with patients,	Phenomena of interest: The idea of empowerment through fostering a sense of control and	$N = 31$. $n = 22$ patients $n = 9$ spouses of patients.	19 semi-structured interviews: combination of individual and joint interviews. 12 individual interviews,	3 themes: 1. Integrating and adapting to TC systems: time adjustment to equipment being bulky/intrusive; interference: TV and electricity	Policy designed to support use of TC has been focused on presumed gains; if PTs are self-reliant, responsible, and motivated through regular

professionals, and policy makers. (Rogers et al., 2011)	confidence forms desire for self-management of long-term conditions.	<i>N</i> = 13 (65 y/o + COPD-11, DM-7, asthma-5, HD-1). 4 sites in England, 1 in Wales.	10 TC users, 2 spouses in PT home, lasting 1–2 hrs, PT observed using equipment. One focus group: 5 users of online asthma consultation, group-compared experiences of equipment use, all audiotaped/ Transcribed; case summaries for each PT, enabled contextual preservation of key ideas, topic guide used.	not individualized to PT 2. Impact of TC on existing illness work-takes time for both users and health care professionals to fit into daily routine 3. Mediating use of relationships with health services: PT felt less of a burden with self-monitoring, PT reliance on TC staff to decrease flareups and hospitalizations.	monitoring: savings in \$ spent, bed days; policy makers need to look at alternatives to traditional visits due to current needs; no longer possible to ignore human aspect of provision of self-care.
Exploring the Effects of Telehealth on Medical Human resources supply in remote regions. (Gagnon et al., 2007)	Delphi consensus panel method.	<i>N</i> = 63: 41 physicians (general practitioners and specialists) 22 managers (hospital managers, recruitment specialists, regional health managers). 4 remote regions of Eastern Quebec. Network contact method, and snowball.	Semi-structured interviews conducted individually or in small groups. Transcripts read by 2 researchers; interview content was coded independently by 2 judges and validated by an expert panel.	Identified 7 categories of recruitment and retention factor: family, community lifestyle, professional, economic, educational, organizational; Lack of medical resources in many countries poses a problem; major concern for decision makers and population. Potential benefits of telehealth will be evident only if the technology is integrated in the organizations and: 1. Fits professional practices, decrease work load to stabilize services 2. Can improve occupational well- being; can be as easy as a	Study provides framework to assess potential influences on medical human resources when planning the future. Authors recommend longitudinal studies to follow the evolution of these effects in stages.

phone call.

3. Can be seen as an asset for recruitment and retention but not perceived as panacea.

Note. TC = Telecare; D/C = discontinue; HTMS = Home Telecare Management System; MED = multiethnic diversity as described by Multicultural Health Unit experts from Sydney, Australia: Anglo/Celtic, Italian, Chinese, Assyrian, Russian, Greek, and South Pacific Islander; FGI = Focus Group Interviews; TAM = Technology Acceptance Model; PT = patient; R/T = related to; M = male; F = female; PARiHS = Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services; MAXQDA = software program designed for computers; IRB = Institutional Review Board; VISN = Veterans Integrated Service Networks; CCRN = Critical Care Registered Nurse.

Summary of Evidence for Quantitative Studies

Purpose (Author/s, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements; Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Young people's views on potential use of telemedicine consultations for sexual health. (Garrett et al., 2011)	Cross sectional. DV: young people's views of telemedicine. IV: first preference: in-person clinician, or telephone/ webcam.	<i>N</i> = 662 aged 16–24 y/o. Australia; convenience sampling.	5-point Likert-type scale: PTs'.1 willingness to use media communication.	85% of sample would be willing to have in-person consultation with doctor, 63% phone consultation, 29% webcam consult. If ≤ 20 min. from clinic, 83% would prefer in-person consultation.	Authors expected an increase in patient's comfort with sexual consultation via media communication if medical companies could reduce privacy and security concerns in the future.

Note. TC = Telecare; D/C = discontinue; HTMS = Home Telecare Management System; MED = multiethnic diversity as described by Multicultural Health Unit experts from Sydney, Australia: Anglo/Celtic, Italian, Chinese, Assyrian, Russian, Greek, and South Pacific Islander; FGI = Focus Group Interviews; TAM = Technology Acceptance Model; PT = patient; R/T = related to; M = male; F = female; PARiHS = Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services; MAXQDA = software program designed for computers; IRB = Institutional Review Board; VISN = Veterans Integrated Service Networks; CCRN = Critical Care Registered Nurse.

APPENDIX B

TABLE: UNIVARIATE ANALYSIS OF LIKERT SCALE QUESTIONS

Table B1

Univariate analysis of Likert scale survey questions

Question	Agree¹ n (%)	Disagree² n (%)
Voluntariness - My boss requires me to use Telehealth	14 (22.2)	49 (77.8)
Voluntariness - Although it might be helpful, using Telehealth is compulsory in my job	16 (25.4)	47 (74.6)
Relative Advantage - Using Telehealth enables me to accomplish tasks more quickly	37 (58.7)	26 (41.3)
Relative Advantage - Using Telehealth improves the quality of the work I do	35 (55.6)	28 (44.4)
Relative Advantage - Using Telehealth makes it easier to do my job	42 (66.7)	21 (33.3)
Relative Advantage - Using Telehealth enhances my effectiveness on the job	43 (68.3)	20 (31.8)
Relative Advantage - Using Telehealth gives me greater control over my work	30 (47.6)	33 (52.4)
Compatibility - Using Telehealth is compatible with all aspects of my work	38 (60.3)	25 (39.7)
Compatibility - I think that using Telehealth fits well with the way I like to work	46 (73.0)	17 (27.0)
Compatibility - Using Telehealth fits into my work style	45 (71.4)	18 (28.6)
Image - People in my organization who use Telehealth have more prestige than those who do not	16 (25.4)	47 (74.6)
Image - People in my organization who use Telehealth have a high profile	19 (30.2)	44 (69.8)
Image - Having use of Telehealth is a status symbol in my organization	25 (39.7)	38 (60.3)
Ease of Use - I believe that it is easy to get Telehealth equipment to do what I want it to do	43 (68.3)	20 (31.8)

Ease of Use - Overall, I believe that Telehealth equipment is easy to use	53 (84.1)	10 (15.9)
Ease of Use - Learning to operate Telehealth equipment is easy for me	54 (85.7)	9 (14.3)
Result Demonstrability - I would have no difficulty telling others about the results of Telehealth	59 (93.7)	4 (6.4)
Result Demonstrability - I believe I could communicate to others the consequences of using Telehealth	56 (88.9)	7 (11.1)
Result Demonstrability - The results of using Telehealth are apparent to me	56 (88.9)	7 (11.1)
Result Demonstrability - I would have difficulty explaining why Telehealth may or may not be beneficial	8 (12.7)	55 (87.3)
Visibility - In my organization, one sees Telehealth in many clinics	48 (76.2)	15 (23.8)
Revised: Visibility - Telehealth is very visible in my organization	50 (79.4)	13 (20.6)
Trialability - Before deciding whether to use any Telehealth equipment, I was able to properly try it out	53 (84.1)	10 (15.9)
Trialability - I was permitted to use Telehealth equipment on a trial basis long enough to see what it could do	52 (82.5)	11 (17.5)

Notes. ¹Agree = Agree/Strongly Agree categories were collapsed; ²Disagree = Neutral/Disagree/Strongly Disagree were collapsed; ³Chi-Square Test for Equal Proportions (Null hypothesis is that the proportions are equal). *Statistically Significant.

APPENDIX C

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH

Factors associated with the successful adoption of Telehealth in A Retail Health Clinic

You are asked to participate in a research study conducted by Elizabeth Ornelas, FNP-BC, MSN from the DNP Consortium at California State University, Long Beach. You are a possible participant in this study because you are involved with telehealth.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this project will be to identify the factors which support successful adoption of telehealth in a retail health clinic.

PROCEDURES

If you volunteer to participate in this study, you will complete a survey that will take about 15 minutes and contain approximately 36 items. You will click on the following link to begin the survey: (link to be created)

POTENTIAL RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

The risk of involvement is minimal but completion of the survey may result in fatigue.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS TO SUBJECTS AND/OR TO SOCIETY

The benefits of participation to the individual are minimal but may include psychological well-being from providing information to improve the quality of care for your patients.

PAYMENT FOR PARTICIPATION

There is no payment for participation in this study.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your responses will not be shared with your supervisor or anyone else in your workplace. Any information obtained in connection with this study that can be identified with you will remain confidential and will be disclosed only with your permission or as required by law.

PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL

You can choose whether to be in this study or not. If you volunteer to be in this study, you may stop at any time without consequences. Participation or non-participation will not affect your employment within this organization or any other personal consideration or right you usually expect. You may also refuse to answer any questions and still remain in the study.

RIGHTS OF RESEARCH SUBJECTS

You are not waiving any legal claims, rights or remedies because of your participation in this research study. If you have questions regarding your rights as a research subject, contact the Office of University Research, CSU Long Beach, 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840; Telephone: (562) 985-5314 or email to irb@csulb.edu. You may also contact:

1. Elizabeth Ornelas, FNP-BC, MSN, Principal Investigator at (949) 280-7962, or email Elizabeth.Ornelas@csu.fullerton.edu.
2. Dr. Joy Goebel, Research Chair at Joy.Goebel@csulb.edu or call (562) 985-1635.

IDENTIFICATION OF INVESTIGATORS

If you have any questions about the research, please feel free to contact Elizabeth Ornelas, FNP-BC, MSN Principal Investigator, Elizabeth.Ornelas@csu.fullerton.edu or Dr. Joy Goebel, Research Chair at Joy.Goebel@csulb.edu.

CONSENT OF RESEARCH SUBJECT

I understand the procedures and conditions of my participation described above. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this study. I may also request a copy of this form by emailing Elizabeth.Ornelas@csu.fullerton.edu.
By taking the survey, I am indicating my consent to participate.

Please click on this survey link to begin.

APPENDIX D
SURVEY QUESTIONS

Factors associated with the successful adoption of Telehealth

Have you participated in the survey before?

- Yes
- No

If Yes, then skip to the end of the survey

1. What is your professional role?

- 1. NP
- 2. LVN/LPN

2. Have you ever worked with telehealth prior to its use in Minute Clinic?

- 1. Yes
- 2. No

3. How would you describe the quality of care delivered via telehealth to patients in your clinic? Select One:

- 1. Excellent
- 2. Good
- 3. Fair
- 4. Poor
- 5. Not Applicable

4. In which county are you currently employed?

- 1. Los Angeles County
- 2. Orange County/ Inland Empire
- 3. San Diego County

5. How many years have you been in practice?

Practice Years:

6. How many months have you utilized telehealth?

Telehealth Months:

7. What is your highest level of education?

- 1. Nursing Diploma (one year LVN/LPN)
- 2. Associate Degree
- 3. Bachelors Degree
- 4. Masters Degree
- 5. Doctoral Degree
- 6. Other _____
- 7. Not Applicable

8. Describe your thoughts about telehealth:

9. Describe your thoughts about how telehealth affects the quality of patient care:

10. Describe your thoughts related to your training or the implementation of telehealth?

1. Voluntariness

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not Applicable
1a. My boss does not require me to use telehealth.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
1b. Although it might be helpful, using telehealth is certainly not compulsory in my job.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6

2. Relative Advantage

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not Applicable
2a. Using telehealth enables me to accomplish tasks more quickly.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
2b. Using telehealth improves the quality of the work I do.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
2c. Using telehealth makes it easier to do my job.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
2d. Using telehealth enhances my effectiveness on the job.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
2e. Using telehealth gives me greater control over my work.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6

3. Compatibility

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not Applicable
3a. Using telehealth is compatible with all aspects of my work.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6

3b. I think that using telehealth fits well with the way I like to work.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
3c. Using telehealth fits into my work style.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6

4. Image

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not Applicable
4a. People in my organization who use telehealth have more prestige than those who do not.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
4b. People in my organization who use telehealth have a high profile.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
4c. Having use of telehealth is a status symbol in my organization.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6

5. Ease of Use

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not Applicable
5a. I believe that it is easy to get telehealth to do what I want it to do.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
5b. Overall, I believe that telehealth is easy to use.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
5c. Learning to operate telehealth is easy for me.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6

6. Result Demonstrability

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not Applicable
6a. I would have no difficulty telling others about the results of using telehealth.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
6b. I believe I could communicate to others the consequences of using telehealth.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
6c. The results of using telehealth are apparent to me.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6

6d. I would have difficulty explaining why telehealth may or may not be beneficial.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
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7. Visibility

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not Applicable
7a. In my organization, one sees telehealth in many clinics.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
7b. Telehealth is not very visible in my organization.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6

8. Trialability

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not Applicable
8a. Before deciding whether to use any telehealth applications, I was able to properly try them out.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6
8b. I was permitted to use telehealth on a trial basis long enough to see what it could do.	<input type="radio"/> 5	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 6

You have completed this survey.

Thank you for your participation! You are welcome to contact us at the email below for questions.

Content Questions:

Elizabeth Ornelas, Principal Investigator at Elizabeth.Ornelas@csu.fullerton.edu